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Data management plan (DMP)

Natural Disaster Trends

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Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	11/05/2023	First version of DMP – created for start of project using the DAMAP tool
2.0	13/05/2023	Second version of DMP – prepared for review

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
EM-DAT	The CRED/OFDA International Disaster Database

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	emdat_transformed.csv	Plain text	csv	5 MB	no
P2	full_analysis.ipynb	Plain text	Jupyter Notebook	10 MB	no

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	NASA GLOBAL LAND-OCEAN TEMPERATURE INDEX	https://data.giss.nasa.gov/gistemp/graphs/graph_data/Global_Mean_Estimates_based_on_Land_and_Ocean_Data/graph.txt	May be used without permission, as long as due credit is provided. See here .	no
R2	World Bank Population Data	https://api.worldbank.org/v2/en/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL?downloadformat=csv	CC BY-4.0	no
R3	The CRED/OFDA International Disaster Database	https://public.emdat.be/data	May be used without permission for academic purposes but not commercial ones. See here .	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The 3 datasets listed will be reused for the analysis.

R1 (NASA GLOBAL LAND-OCEAN TEMPERATURE INDEX): This dataset has been downloaded from https://data.giss.nasa.gov/gistemp/graphs/graph_data/Global_Mean_Estimates_based_on_Land_and_Ocean_Data/graph.txt and converted to a common csv format. In order to reproduce this, line 1-3 and 5 have to be removed and the string " " (for spaces) replaced by "," for the entire document. The resulting csv file is to be saved as "data/nasa_yearly_global_temperature.csv" in the project directory sourced from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7930475>.

R2 (World Bank Population Data): This dataset provides population data from the World Bank API. The current data can be at <https://api.worldbank.org/v2/en/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL?downloadformat=csv>. In order to reuse it with our code, the downloaded zip file has to be unzipped and the file starting with "API_SP.POP.*" saved to the "data/population.csv" directory.

R3 (The CRED/OFDA International Disaster Database EM-DAT): The primary focus is on the EM-DAT dataset which is downloaded from <https://public.emdat.be/data> with a filter on Disaster Classification set to only include Natural Disaster with all subtypes. In order to rerun our code with a newly downloaded file, it has to be renamed to "emda.xlsx" and moved to the "data/" repository. The data inside the excel file is transformed to a new dataset emdat_transformed.csv initially using python 3, jupyter notebook and pandas (~=1.5.2). There is no DOI available for this dataset.

The produced dataset (P2) is stored in the csv (comma separated values) format and UTF-8 encoding. The file uses up less than 2MB of storage space as of the state of the EM-DAT dataset (R3) in 2023 and includes 16 features/columns. An alternative source for disaster data considered was the Mortality Database provided by the WHO, however, it was discarded because it lacks distinction of natural disaster categories and also has a limited history of 50 years compared to the 100+ years in the EM-DAT dataset.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

Version control is automated using git and github.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at file level especially for the R2 and P1 datasets. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

The documentation of the applied methodology with details on the individual steps performed is saved alongside the python 3 code in the jupyter notebook full_analysis.ipynb.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: data entry validation.

Individual rows of the EM-DAT dataset (R3) have been and will be checked individually on a random basis. Especially natural disasters that correspond to an outlier in a certain feature have been verified:

- Drought in China (1928): more political than natural (warlords using grain for themselves, less production due to opium plantation); Reference: <https://disasterhistory.org/the-northwest-china-famine-1928-1930>
- Epidemic in India (1920): Encephalitis lethargica; Reference <https://simplifiedupsc.in/epidemics-that-have-hit-india-since-1900/>
- Drought in Soviet Union (1921): natural and human caused - (Civil War, Russian Revolution: confiscation of stored grain) ; Reference: <https://www.norkarussia.info/famine-1921-1924.html>
- Viral disease (1926): Spanish flu brought back from soldiers; Reference: <https://simplifiedupsc.in/epidemics-that-have-hit-india-since-1900/>
- Drought in China (1920): rainless 12 months - total failure of Harvest; Reference: <http://disasterhistory.org/north-china-famine-1920-21>

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

R1 (NASA GLOBAL LAND-OCEAN TEMPERATURE INDEX), R2 (World Bank Population Data), R3 (The CRED/OFDA International Disaster Database) will be stored in Github. External storage will be used because the required TUWien institutional storage, i.e. the tuGitLab, does not allow the research team to create a new repository for backups because we are all students.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	no access
P2	writing	writing	no access
R1	writing	writing	no access
R2	writing	writing	no access
R3	writing	writing	no access

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	license
P1	Open	Embargo before publishing	2023-06-29	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7930539	CC BY-NC 4.0
P2	Open	Embargo before publishing	2023-06-29	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7930475	GPL-3.0

Methods or software needed to access and use data: Potential users need no specific software tools in order to reuse the data except for a tool to read a UTF-8 csv file. For reading the textual analysis and visualizations, a pdf-reader is required. However, in order to reperform the following tools are needed:

- Python 3.8+
- Jupyter Notebook

and the following python 3 pip packages:

- matplotlib~=3.6.2
- numpy~=1.24.1
- openpyxl~=3.0.10
- pandas~=1.5.2
- seaborn~=0.12.2
- bokeh~=2.4.3
- geopandas~=0.12.2

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	Github	10 years	Students and general public interested in natural disaster trends and potential causes.
P2	Github	10 years	

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The data officer and project officer Moritz Renkin will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The lead country researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
-	-	-	-	-
Estimated total costs				0